

Short communication

On the presence of *Perillus bioculatus* (Fabricius, 1775) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Pentatomidae: Asopinae) in Slovenia

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Abstract. *Perillus bioculatus* (Fabricius, 1775) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Pentatomidae: Asopinae) is reported for the first time in Slovenia. The distribution of the species in Europe is summarised, and its current spread is discussed.

Key words: true bugs, Pentatomoidea, distribution, new record, Europe, Mediterranean Region, Slovenia.

So far, the Nearctic bug species *Perillus bioculatus* (Fabricius, 1775) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Pentatomidae: Asopinae), which was introduced to various European countries as a biological pest control in attempts to control the invasive Colorado Potato Beetle *Leptinotarsa decemlineata* (Say, 1824) (Kóbor & Brhane 2024; van der Heyden et al. 2024), has been reported as present in the following European countries: Austria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Kosovo, Moldova, North Macedonia, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Türkiye and Ukraine (Ćato et al. 2024; van der Heyden et al. 2024; Aukema 2025; van der Heyden 2025).

Fig. 1. Specimen of *Perillus bioculatus* (Fabricius, 1775), Griblje, Črnomelj, Slovenia (photo: Milea Lasthein).

Herein, the presence of *P. bioculatus* in Slovenia is reported: On 21.09.2025, an adult specimen (Fig. 1) was found in the village of Griblje, located in the municipality of Črnomelj in the southern part of the country near the border with Croatia (coordinates: 45.5660783333, 15.2970416667, accuracy: 4 m).

A photo of the specimen was uploaded to the online database iNaturalist (Lasthein 2025a).

On 18.10.2025, another adult specimen of *P. bioculatus* was discovered nearby at the same location (coordinates: 45.5660833333, 15.2971366667, accuracy: 4 m). Four photographs of the specimen were uploaded to the online database iNaturalist (Lasthein 2025b).

This discovery of *P. bioculatus* in Slovenia aligns with the ongoing westward expansion of the species described by van der Heyden et al. (2024).

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